

EVALUATION OF THE TWO-YEAR PRE-SERVICE B.ED. PROGRAMME IN ODISHA WITH REFERENCE TO STRUCTURE AND CURRICULUM DESIGN: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

Abstract:

The study aims to assess the extent to which the existing two-year B.Ed. programme in Odisha fulfils expectations of NCFTE-2009 with respect to duration, working days, admission procedures, intake capacity and fee structure under the purview of structure and curriculum design as the teacher education has undergone significant structural and curricular transformation in India.

A descriptive research design was adopted. Thirty-four retired teacher education experts with more than fifteen years of professional experience were selected through purposive sampling. The programme was analyzed against the norms and standards prescribed by NCFTE-2009.

The findings reveal that most Teacher Training Institutions (TTIs) in Odisha comply with NCFTE-2009 regarding programme duration, working days, attendance norms, curriculum design. Admission procedures are largely regulated through a centralized entrance examination conducted by TE and SCERT, though certain autonomous self-financing colleges follow merit-based selection. The curriculum has been comprehensive with increased emphasis on practicum and community engagement. However, gaps persist in faculty strength, infrastructural facilities, research culture, and uniformity in admission practices. The study suggested for ensuring adequate staffing, and enhancing infrastructural and research support systems to align more effectively with NCFTE-2009 expectations.

Information about the authors

Dr. Pradipta Kumar Mishra,
Professor-cum-Principal, Yogoda Satsanga Palpara Mahavidyalaya (NAAC Accredited – B++), Palpara, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India

Introduction:

Quality Education through Quality Schooling is on the spotlight of discussion in the visualization of Policy makers, Planners, Politicians, Educationists, Administrators, Psychologists, etc. In this regard, pre-service teacher orientation programme is a must for every individual seeking to have his/her career in teaching particularly with reference to school education.

The Pre Service Teacher Education Programme (PTEP) is being imparted from the Pre-Primary Level to Post-Graduate Level. Pre-Primary and Innovative Teacher Education Programme act as an integrated Programme. These two Programmes are now signifying the importance of the PTEP on which research needs to be conducted. Apart from this, the Govt. of India has already been approved this to be universalized by 2030 in an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary manner along with the 1-

year B.Ed. Programme with Post-Graduation degree as the eligibility criteria again with the existing 2-year B.Ed. Programme approved in the NEP -2020.

1.1.1. National Education Policy -2020 on Teacher Education

NEP 2020 stresses on the multidisciplinary teaching and training for the student teachers in order to make them to be competent and effective teachers embedded with human values, ethics, Indian traditions through teacher education. As a result, teachers will be fit both in scholastic and co-scholastic perspectives.

Only academically sound, interdisciplinary, and integrated teacher preparation programmes shall be in use by 2030. All teacher education programmes must incorporate multidisciplinary components and instruction both in high-quality curriculum and pedagogy. A 4-year integrated teacher education programme should replace all standalone TEIs by 2030. This programme will be offered in colleges and institutions with multidisciplinary education departments. The four-year Integrated Teacher Education Programme needs to be actualised along with 2 year and 1 year B.Ed. programme by 2030 as mandated by NEP 2020.

The government will make subject matter experts available to TEIs. Each TEI should have a direct link with both government and private schools. Admission to the pre-service programme will be done through a test conducted by the National Testing Agency (NTA) named National Common Entrance Test (NCET). Faculty with high expertise in different subject areas and a research wing will be highly valued. Technology must be used in this training programme to strengthen teachers' educational value.

1.1.2. Present Status of Teacher Education in India

Teacher Education in India got a shape after the establishment of NCTE as a Statutory Body in 1995. Afterwards, it regulates all types of Teacher Education Programmes in Country through formulation of Norms and Standards in 2005, 2007, 2009 and at last in 2014 and subsequent amendments from time to time. The development of NCFTE, 2009 regarded as the milestone striving to maintain the standard in teacher education leading to quality. As of June 30, 2022, there were 16917 teacher education institutions operating as NCTE recognised institutions at the various levels of teacher education, of which 15,563 are private institutions. This is because 92 percent of the institutions that are available to provide teacher education are in the private sector, and 88 percent of those institutions deal with diploma level programmes and 96 percent with secondary level programmes. It indicates the commercialisation of teacher education in India in a high degree.

The primary educational organisation in India for school education is called NCERT, and its state counterpart, SCERT, is in charge of teacher preparation. In last few years the teacher education has been going on through SSA, subsequently RTE-SSA Scheme now as Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan. The programme was run from pre-primary to intermediate level of education. It also included the in-service teacher's training programme for teachers in their service.

1.1.3. Status of Teacher Education in Odisha

Since the beginning of teacher education in Odisha, the D.El.Ed., B.Ed., B.P.Ed., and M.Ed. programmes have been administered by TE and SCERT as the academic body. On January 15, 1990, this department was recognized as an Independent Directorate. Before then, the State Institute of Education (SIE), founded in 1964, and SCERT, founded in 1979, were used. The Board of Secondary Education in Odisha is the examining body for the D.El.Ed. programme, the examining bodies for the B.Ed. and M.Ed. courses are the universities to which the Teacher Education Institutions are affiliated.

In 1990–1991 the Department of Education and Youth Services oversaw the operation of 52 ST Schools, 11 DIETs, 2 IASEs, and 3 CTEs. In June 1990 the SCERT renamed as TE and SCERT. There were 1487 teacher educators in elementary schools received training in the teaching and learning

process in 1989–1990, while 171 teacher educators in secondary schools were exposed to fresh approaches to instruction. A total of 2400 primary and high school teachers participated in 62 training programmes to enhance scientific instruction.

In the State of Odisha, there are currently 30 DIETs, 4 BIETs, 34 ETEIs, and 1 Hindi TTI.

NCTE – The Statutory Body of Teacher Education

Since 1973, the NCTE (National Council for Teacher Education) has been a non-profit organisation dedicated to teacher education. The NCTE has served as a consultative body to the government in the field of teacher education.

According to NPE 1986, it has entered into force and serves as a statutory body in the field of teacher education. The head office and its regional bodies have administrative control over the TEIs and also serve as academic wings, assisting the TEIs with innovations, policy development, curriculum planning and implementation, research, and financial assistance.

The functions of NCTE are as follows:

- Carry out research on a variety of topics related to teacher preparation, publish the findings, and conduct surveys.
- To guide in planning for suitable teacher education plans and programmes.
- Coordinate and keep track of how the nation's teacher preparation programmes are progressing.
- Specify the minimal requirements for employment as a teacher in educational facilities or other recognised organisations.
- Establish standards for various training programmes.
- Establish standards for admission eligibility criteria and the selection process for candidates
- It emphasizes the guidelines for curriculum development;
- It emphasizes the guidelines for establishing a new institution or course.
- It also emphasizes the criteria for examination pattern for teacher education.

Review of Related Studies:

Sao and Behera (2016) reported that lack of favourable attitude has been observed among the B.Ed. student teachers in relation to their gender, habitation and management variation towards the 2 -year B.Ed. Programme.

Khan (2016) revealed that the teacher trainees of Department of Education, Aligarh Muslim University expressed unfavourable experience on the said Programme from the standpoint of its facilities and implementation of the curriculum along with the school internship ,whereas, the teacher educators have expressed their balanced view on the programme although it is a good initiative they viewed which can be transacted smoothly through proper organisation.

Khan (2017) found out that teacher educators have not shown so much favourable or unfavourable attitude towards the 2 -year B.Ed. Curriculum, but they have shown clear unfavourable experience in the overall organisation of this programme with focus on the “school internship” of six months due to the negligible attitude of both govt and private secondary schools for the said purpose.

Adhikary (2017) conducted a study on the teacher trainees of Assam revealed that lack of balance in the curriculum design with regard to theory and practice and complexity have been observed and teacher education needs to be a core paper rather an optional paper, dissatisfied with the fee structure, job guarantee etc. However, they have shown a mixed perception towards the said Programme.

Ahmad and Sharma (2017) observed that the B.Ed. Students are of view that quantity does not matter rather quality of the programme matters irrespective of its duration.

Bajaj and Sangha (2017) found that some components of practical work overlapped with field work, and obstacles associated with school engagement include the fact that, while the period has been expanded, the activities that must be completed are difficult to implement in schools. Many schools believe that Pedagogical Teaching by B.Ed. students will negatively impact their students' performance, affecting overall results.

Pakira and Khan (2018) found measurable difference among the teacher trainees having UG and PG Degree and the same trend also among the pre and in-service teacher trainees towards the programme.

Sahoo and Behera (2018) reported that the curriculum framework of the 2-Year B.Ed. Programme is not in line with the NCFTE,2009. Notable among them are reflection, critical examination, integration, questioning and social and personal realities of curriculum transaction.

Prakash (2019) reported that urban student teachers are better than the rural student teachers in the dimension of teaching-learning process due to the exposure of urban counterparts to different methods of teaching with other opportunities, whereas, the student teachers of joint family norm have better attitude than the nuclear family counterparts because of their adaptability and adjustability with the regular and any situations of the family.

Ramakrishna (2020) found that the teacher educators of one University College of Education and two affiliated Colleges of Education affiliated to Osmania University have extended their highly satisfactory view on the components of the said course to be aligned with NEP 2020 along with school internship.

The dimensions of teaching – learning process of the 2-Year B.Ed. course has not been influenced or affected by “Gender” and “Habitation” variation in West Bengal reported by Halder (2021).

Gorain and Pradhan (2021) in a study on Odisha reported that the norms and standards with regard to intake ,eligibility, and admission procedure curriculum ,assessment ,basic scale of pay, have been adhered as per NCTE norms and standards ,whereas, student attendance for course work and school internship, availability of instructional facilities like laboratory facilities, art and resource centre, library cum resource centre, health and physical resources etc are negligible as per NCTE norms and standards perceived by both the student teachers and teacher educators .

Sharma (2022) reported that the School Internship of the curriculum encouraged active learning ,engagement of learners with the field work were properly evaluated for which more efforts need to be undertaken to make the internship practices reflective in reality through internship activities.

In his research on the 2-year B.Ed. curriculum, Jayakumar (2016) covered the significance of teaching-learning process in catering educational expectations and needs in school education, notably at the secondary school level.

Think Tank and SCERT (2014) conducted a study on "Public Opinion on Reforming Teacher Education in Odisha" observed that a one-year B.Ed. curriculum is insufficient for a professional course, and the reason for this is because students were admitted late to the programme. Again, it was a lengthy course that required additional time. The majority of respondents (86 percent) favoured the ITEP over one B.Ed. Course.

Kumari and Panda (2013) reported that the B.Ed. programme was based on cognitive viewpoints, and lack of infrastructural facilities was a difficulty in achieving the B.Ed. curriculum's goal.

Yadav (2011) found that the curriculum was set up as a theoretical programme rather than a practical one. Additionally, he said that the B.Ed. and school curricula were not coordinated and that the program's length should be increased to two years.

In 2011, Padhi and Kumar concluded that (i) theory and practical papers need to be distributed fairly within the curriculum and (ii) a two-year teacher training programme has to be put in place to develop students' training aptitudes. (iii) the internship is characterised by its duration, local research project, outreach programmes, regular conferences, seminars, and group discussions should be held at regular intervals to build competencies of teacher trainees.

Rastogi & Goel (2010) reported that the current teacher education system was distinguished by a lack of adequate classroom experience. It had a beneficial impact on the newly hired teachers' attitudes about the teaching-learning process, and it was an important element of their professional growth.

According to Mohanty's (2008) study on school improvement, teacher empowerment, and teacher education, the teacher education the aspects like faculty demonstration lessons, library and reading room operation, classroom teaching observation, interaction with this stakeholders, demonstration lessons, governing council and heads of practice teaching schools.

Singh and Gardia (2006), who undertook a study to analyse and develop the B. Ed. curriculum, reported that teacher education should place a greater emphasis on developing topics like education for peace, entrepreneurship, challenging internships, and environmental concerns in citizenship.

Goswami (2007) claimed for need based teacher education qualitatively with increasing the number of days available for internship classes, as well as a strict guidelines. Faculty should adopt innovative or new teaching-learning strategies, and student teachers should be properly oriented on action research.

It is essential leading to quality schooling to be resulted in producing effective teachers and reflective practitioners with competency, efficiency and proficiency for which the structure and organisation of the programme needs to be systematically organised justified by Padhi and Kumar(2011),Rastogi and Goel(2010),Ahmad and Sharma (2017) and Sharma (2022).The Curriculum needs to be organised as per the NCFTE,2009 with emphasis on perspectives or foundations, pedagogy and school internship advocated by Sahoo and Behera(2018),Adhikary(2017),Yadav (2011),Goswami and Pradhan(2021), Kumari and Panda(2013), Bajaj and Sangha(2017), Khan(2017), Ramakrishna(2020). Besides, emphasis should be on the School Internship in order to make the student teachers reflective practitioners and effective teachers in their real teaching world reported by Goswami(2007), Mohanty(2008), Singh and Gardia (2006), Khan(2017), Gorain and Pradhan(2021), and Sharma (2022)

Significance:

The curriculum development as per the principle of balance, infrastructure and instructional facilities and most importantly is the school internship as a major part of Curriculum transaction advocated by Padhi and Kumar(2011), Rastogi and Goel(2010), Ahmad and Sharma(2017), Mohanty(2008), Goswami(2007), Sharma(2022). The structure and organisation of the Curriculum needs to be developed intact as per NCFTE,2009 with emphasis on critical examination of text books, integration of scholastic and co-scholastic activities by wiping out the challenges for acceleration of innovative teaching practices lamented by Sahoo and Behera(2018), Adhikary(2017) and accept Teacher Education in India as a Core paper rather than an optional one justified by Yadav (2011).But the norms and standards with regard to intake, eligibility, admission procedure, basic scale of pay of teacher educators are satisfactory reported by Gorain and Pradhan(2021).However, the challenges of this 2-year course in the light of its structure and feasibility like lack of infrastructure and instructional facilities like laboratory, art and resource centre, library -cum-resource centre, health and physical resources need to be taken care of properly argued by Kumari and Panda(2013), Gorain and

Pradhan(2021).The Challenges with regard to the curriculum like overlapping of content , a lack of logical topic sequencing ,and lack of content demarcation ,lack of focus on action research project ,regular conferences, seminars, and group discussions to enhance the quality of the programme, acceleration of innovative approaches, acceptance of multidisciplinary contexts , lack of proper organisation of curricular activities, more theoretical with complex papers advocated by Bajaj and Sangha(2017), Padhi and Kumar(2011), Sahoo and Behera(2018), Khan(2017), Adhikary(2017)and Ramakrishna(2020).

School Internship as a major component of the 2-year B.Ed Curriculum needs attention with regard to classroom teaching observation, demonstration lessons, the no. of days for internship, organisational framework, engagement with the field work, scope of feedback from the school teachers on the school internship ,school organisation and management reported by Goswami(2007),Mohanty(2008),Singh and Gardia(2006), Khan(2017), Gorain and Pradhan(2021) and Sharma(2022).

Objective:

To evaluate the 2-Year Pre-Service B.Ed Programme in the light of NCFTE,2009 with regard to its Structure and Curriculum design.

Research Questions:

1. How does the Programme fulfil expectations of NCFTE,2009 in duration perspective?
2. How does it fulfil expectations of NCFTE, 2009 from standpoint of working days?
3. How does it fulfil expectations of NCFTE,2009 from admission point of view?
4. How does this programme fulfil expectations of NCFTE,2009 with regard to its intake capacity and fee structure?
5. How does this Programme fulfil expectations of NCFTE,2009 from the standpoint of curriculum design?

Methodology of Study

The researcher has selected 34 Experts from Teacher Education those who have taken retirement from their job and have more than 15 years of teaching career in the concerned field. 34 Experts were selected through Purposive Sampling procedure.

The researcher analysed aspects like its structure including duration, working days, admission, intake capacity and fees and curriculum design in the light of the NCFTE-2009 for getting a functional view on it.

Result and Discussion:

This study was analysed with regard to its duration, working days, admission, Intake Capacity and fee structure under the purview of Structure and Curriculum design, as per the NCFTE-2009

Norms and Standards of 2-Year B.Ed. Programme on Duration as per

NCFTE-2009 reads that; the shift from one year course to two year; the curriculum to be approachable with the 4 year course; assessment of the programme as a regular practice to make it updated and specific to the local, regional, and state needs.

2-Year B.Ed. Programme on Working Days as per NCFTE-2009

According to NCFTE, 2009 guidelines, there must be at least 200 working days, excluding the time for testing and admission. The institution must put in at least 36 hours of work per week (5 or 6 days). The

required minimum attendance for student teacher is 80 percent for all theory and practicum sessions, and 90 percent for school internships.

All the Teacher Training Institutions are following 200 working days for one year and 36 hours or more than it for 5-6 working days in a week. For attendance the institutions are framing some rules specifically absence from community functions, observation days, i.e., Independence Day, Republic Day, Cultural Functions, Debates, Seminars are treated seriously.

2-Year B.Ed. Programme on Admission as per NCFTE-2009

- By developing state-specific methodologies, determine the predominant entry qualification of applicants for pre-service programmes.
- Initiatives will be launched to develop appropriate procedures to encourage the enrollment of talented individuals in teacher education programmes.

A common entrance examination conducted by the TE & SCERT in the State of Odisha as a requirement for candidates for admission is done. The candidates must have earned a Bachelor's or Master's Degree in the Science, Arts or commerce with a minimum cumulative grade point average of 50% for general candidates and a minimum of 45% for SC/ST/SEBC/other reserved candidates. Candidates who have earned a B.Tech. degree and have earned a minimum of a 55 percent aggregate score for the general category or a 50 percent score for the reserved category are eligible for the programme. They must have earned a minimum of 200 marks in at least two academic subjects for their Bachelor's degree. The same application is open to applicants who are taking the final-year exam or are awaiting the results. For general category maximum age limit is 28 years, for Women / SC/ST/SEBC/Other category the maximum age limit is 33-years and for Physically Handicapped, it is 38 years.

However, 12 Autonomous colleges are also providing 2-year B.Ed. Programme in Self-financing mode and they are not following the Entrance Examination and only Mark basis selection is followed by them for admission into B.Ed. Programme after getting permission from NCTE.

2-Year B.Ed. Programme on Intake Capacity and Fee Structure as per

NCFTE-2009:

For a school subject method paper and practical exercises, not more than 25 students should be assigned to a teacher in a basic unit of 50 students with a minimum of two units. The institution may only charge fees that are authorized by the State Government or other relevant affiliating authority in compliance with NCTE guidelines. Donations, capitation fees, and other payments may not be collected from student teachers.

The state-operated teacher training institutions' intake capacity complies with NCTE standards. A basic unit consists of 50 pupils. The fee structure of the programme varies with reference to the management of the institution.

Table No. 1: Distribution of Fee structure for 2-year B.Ed. and 4-Year Integrated B.Ed. Programme in different TTIs of Odisha

	University			Govt. Auto. College		Teacher Training Institutes		District Institutes for Education and Training	
	1 st year	2 nd year		1 st year	2 nd year	1 st year	2 nd year	1 st year	2 nd year
2- year B.Ed. Programme	45000/-	45000/-		45000/-	45000/-	4700/-	4256/-	4700/-	4256/-
4- Year Integrated B.Ed.	Utkal University	Ravenshaw University	SCS, Puri	FM Auto College,	RIE, BBSR	MPC Auto College Baripada		GM University, Sambalpur	

Programme per annum				Balasore			
	50000/-	50000/-	40000/-	40000/-	14155/-	31750/-	32129/-

Curriculum design in relation to

NCFTE-2009:

- Teachers' language skills need to be improved.
- Student teachers should receive education from viewpoints that foster principles for peace, uphold human rights for all, and honour and value labour.
- Connecting curricula with formal school knowledge and including locally relevant topics.
- Pre-service and in-service teachers can benefit from ICT for their professional growth and academic support.
- The three main curricular areas that make up the curriculum for teacher education are school internship, curriculum and pedagogy, and foundation of education.
- It is recommended that curriculum for teacher education should incorporate health awareness, yoga, and meditation along with sports and physical education in toto.
- Specific practicum courses for student teachers should be carried out in the form of projects, group discussion, field trips and other community based collective activities.
- To concentrate on philosophical thoughts and philosopher's personalities, theoretical frameworks that support educational objectives and epistemological issues as well should be incorporated in the curriculum.

Discussion:

It is observed by the researcher that in Odisha all the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) are following the guidelines of NCFTE-2009 regarding its duration of two years from academic session 2015-16. There are also 4 universities, 12 autonomous colleges where this course is running along with 4-year Integrated Teacher Education Programme is also followed by 3 Universities and 3 Autonomous Colleges and by RIE, (NCERT) Bhubaneswar.

All the TEIs are following 200 working days for one year and 36 hours or more than it for 5-6 working days in a week. A candidate is admitted through the common entrance test conducted by TE & SCERT with having all the essential eligibility criteria like educational qualification, age limit, and marks obtained, having 2 school subjects, etc. Minimum 80% attendance in theory and practicum and 90% attendance in school internship for student teachers is following strictly.

However, Some Autonomous colleges are also providing 2-year B.Ed. Programme in Self-financing mode and they are not following the Entrance Examination and only Mark basis selection is followed by them for the admission into the Programme. There is basic unit of 50 students. In colleges where B.Ed. programme is going-on in Self-financing mode the fee structure depends mostly on their own decision but in average it's all about 90,000/ for two academic years.

The present B.Ed. Curriculum comprises three broad curriculum areas as per the framework envisaged in NCFTE-2009 and scope of tasks and assignments in each theory paper. There is a scope of Community Activity, Skill Development Work and School Internship Programme in the B.Ed. Course for engagement of trainees.

There is annual system of evaluation for every academic year conducted by the University. The assessment follows the CCE pattern of evaluation where Internal and External examination is there. Student teachers are also assessed by their Project Work, Assignments, Tasks, Portfolio activities,

Community activities. The institutions are organizing different seminars, workshops, talks, debates, etc for capacity building development of the stakeholders.

On account of the staff position it is observed that there is faculty crunch as per the Norms and Standards as per the NCFTE, 2009. Many Institutions are running with the help of the Guest Faculty.

Although every TEIs has the necessary infrastructural facilities but many have no art and craft resource centre, health and physical education resource centre, canteen facility along with reading room facilities. Besides, some institutions have insufficient classrooms and playground facilities.

This Programme is essential from stand point of its duration, scholastic and co-scholastic activities including assignments as practicum. This observation of the Researcher in this study is in line with the studies conducted by Bajaj and Sangha (2017), Jaykumar (2016), Rastogi & Goel (2010), Yadav (2011), Ahmad & Sharma (2017). In order to make a teacher to be a skilled and competent, emphasis should be given on school internship observed in the study which is in line with the findings of the studies conducted by Padhi and Kumar (2011), Mishra (2010), Goswami (2007), Kumari and Panda (2013), Adhikary (2017), Khan (2017), Sahoo and Behera (2018), Gorain and Pradhan (2021) and Sharma (2021). Regular appointment of Teacher Educators across the Country including Odisha is highly required for the said programme as per opinion of Teacher Education Experts which has also been observed in the studies conducted by Think Tank and SCERT (2014), Kumari and Panda (2013), Sahoo and Behera (2018), and Sharma (2022).

Therefore, the evaluation of this course is highly needed as per the opinion of teacher education experts of odisha in response to the expectations of NCFTE 2009.

Implications of the Study:

1. Necessary steps need to be taken for appointment of regular teaching and non-teaching staff for teacher education institutions.
2. Steps will be taken for introduction of Paper on “Specialization in Gifted Children” and a paper on “Language across the Curriculum”.
3. Steps will be taken for Infrastructural Development of the Teacher Education Institutions.
4. Scope for Large Placement will be created.
5. To make B.Ed. Programme in Self-financing mode less expensive proper action should be taken.
6. Emphasis on co-scholastic activities need to be emphasized while redesigning the curriculum.

Conclusion:

The evaluation of this Pre-Service B.Ed. Programme in Odisha indicates that the structural transition from its duration point of view as envisaged in NCFTE-2009, has been largely implemented in letter and spirit. The programme demonstrates compliance in terms of duration, working days, attendance requirements, curriculum organization, and internship provisions. The integration of theory and practicum, community engagement activities, and continuous comprehensive evaluation reflects a progressive orientation toward quality teacher preparation.

Nevertheless, certain critical challenges remain. Variations in admission procedures among autonomous self-financing institutions, shortage of regular faculty members, reliance on guest lecturers, and infrastructural inadequacies limit the optimal realization of programme objectives. Furthermore, there is a need to strengthen ICT integration, research engagement, reflective practices, and continued capacity building development facilities for professional development of teacher educators.

Hence, in order to respond effectively to the evolving vision of teacher education under contemporary reforms, the programme must move beyond structural compliance toward qualitative enhancement. Strengthening institutional capacity, expanding internship experiences, ensuring transparent and merit-based admissions, promoting research culture, and providing adequate infrastructural and academic support will be crucial.

In conclusion, while the Two-Year B.Ed. Programme in Odisha marks a significant step toward qualitative improvement, continuous evaluation, reform, and innovation are essential to produce effective teachers in order to address the challenges and meet the dynamic needs of school education in India.

References

1. Adhikary, A. (2017). A study on the perception of the teacher trainees towards two year B.Ed programme implemented in the teacher education institutions in Assam. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(9), 385–388.
2. Bajaj, R., & Sangha, M. (2017). Challenges in implementation of new curriculum with reference to B.Ed of GGSIPU. *Amity International Journal of Teacher Education*, 3(1).
3. Gorain, R., & Pradhan, S. (2021). Status of pre-service secondary teacher education programme in government institutions under self-finance scheme in Odisha. *International Educational Scientific Research Journal*, 7(1), 76–81.
4. Goswami, D. (2007). Student-teachers' perception of quality teacher education. *Indian Journal of Teacher Education*, 4(1), 29–37.
5. Halder, K. C. (2021). Student teachers' attitude towards two-year B.Ed programme in West Bengal. *International Journal of Management and Social Science Research Review*, 8(2), 22–26.
6. Jayakumar, R. (2016). Pros and cons: Two-year B.Ed programme in India. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education*, 1(1), 76–79.
7. Khan, M. (2017). Implementation of two-year B.Ed programme: Issues and concerns. *Paripex – Indian Journal of Research*, 6(3), 573–576.
8. Kumari, S., & Panda, S. C. (2013). Pre-requisites of pre-service secondary teacher education programme in Jharkhand: An analysis. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(3), 159–172.
9. Mohanty, B. S. (2008). Research priorities in teacher education in India. *Anweshika: Indian Journal of Teacher Education*, 5(1).
10. National Council for Teacher Education. (2009). *National curriculum framework for teacher education: Towards preparing professional and humane teacher*. National Council for Teacher Education.
11. Padhi, S., & Kumar, S. (2011). Growth and status of secondary teacher education programme in Chhattisgarh: A study. *Journal of Indian Education*, 37(2), 70–84.
12. Pakira, J., & Khan, S. (2018). Perception of trainee teachers towards two-year B.Ed programme with respect to some determinants. *Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 8(Special Issue), 36–44.
13. Prakash, S. (2019). Attitude towards two year B.Ed programme of student teachers. *EduSpectra*, 1(2), 9–12.

14. Ramakrishna, A. (2020). Teacher educators' feedback on 2-year B.Ed curriculum for National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 10(4), 109–116.
15. Rastogi, A., & Goel, C. (2010). Effectiveness of school experience programme in building attitude of prospective teachers. *Indian Educational Review*, 46(1), 101–111.
16. Sahoo, J., & Behera, L. (2018). Perspectives of student teachers and teacher educators on pre-service secondary level teacher education programme of Odisha. *Pedagogy of Learning*, 4(3), 32–45.
17. Sao, S., & Behera, S. K. (2016). Student-teachers' attitude towards two-year B.Ed programme with reference to NCTE Regulations 2014. *Pedagogy of Learning*, 2(3), 9–24.
18. Sharma, P. (2022). Student teachers' and teacher educators' perception towards internship and evaluation process in B.Ed programme. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 10(50), 12430–12441.
19. Singh, S. K., & Gardia, A. (2006). Evaluation of existing B.Ed curriculum to develop a new curriculum for secondary level teacher education (Unpublished minor research project). Faculty of Education, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
20. Think Tank-TE & SCERT. (2014). *Directorate of teacher education and State Council of Educational Research and Training*. SCERT, Odisha.
21. Yadav, S. K. (2011). A comparative study of pre-service teacher education programme at secondary stage in Bangladesh, India, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. *Journal of Indian Education*, 48(1).